

Acid Hydrolysis of Benzamides

M. S. SHINGARE, D. B. INGLE and D. D. KHANOLKAR

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad

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Kinetics of acid hydrolysis of benzamide, *m*-nitrobenzamide and *p*-methylbenzamide have been studied in 0.5M to 5M perchloric acid at 95°. The effect of acid concentration and ionic strength on the rate of hydrolysis has been investigated. Arrhenius parameters are calculated to know the mechanism of acid hydrolysis of amides and effect of substituents in benzamides.

KINETICS of hydrolysis of amides have been studied by a number of workers¹⁻³ and shown to involve a SN² mechanism⁴. The present paper deals with the kinetic study of acid hydrolysis of benzamide, *m*-nitrobenzamide and *p*-methylbenzamide.

Materials and Method

The amides used were benzamide, *m*-nitrobenzamide and *p*-methylbenzamide. They were prepared by the reaction of thionylchloride with corresponding acids. The acid chloride thus obtained gives on treatment with strong ammonia or ammonium carbonate, the corresponding amide. The amides were recrystallized from a mixture of alcohol and water. They were tested for purity by checking their melting points which were: Benzamide 128°, *m*-nitrobenzamide 142° and *p*-methylbenzamide 158°. The ionic strength was adjusted with perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate. The other materials were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality and their solutions were prepared in distilled water.

In all the kinetic measurements the concentration of amides were as follows: Benzamide 0.4M, *m*-nitrobenzamide 0.2918M, *p*-methylbenzamide 0.1M. Each reaction mixture was prepared in a thermostat from solutions of known concentration. The temperature was controlled within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Aliquots (usually 5 ml) were drawn at regular intervals and were analysed for ammonia using Sorenson's formal titration method⁵.

Results and Discussion

Effect of concentration of the substrate :

The rate of hydrolysis of benzamides was studied at two different concentrations of amides at 95°. The reaction rate conformed to first order. The rate coefficient in benzamide hydrolysis was found to be independent of its concentration as shown in Table 1.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF SUBSTRATE ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF BENZAMIDE IN PERCHLORIC ACID AT 95°

Benzamide	HClO ₄	K × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
0.4M	1M	3.418
0.5M	1M	3.420
0.4M	2M	5.362
0.5M	2M	5.378

Effect of acid concentration on reaction rate :

The rate constants showed an increase with increase in acid concentration and an optimum value at 3M for benzamide and 2M for both *m*-nitrobenzamide and *p*-methylbenzamide as seen in Fig. 1. Similar rate maxima are reported for the hydrolysis of other amides¹⁻³.

Fig. 1. Plots of rate constants vs acid concentrations.

- ⊙ Benzamide
- ⊗ *m*-nitrobenzamide
- △ *p*-methylbenzamide.

The optimum rate for hydrolysis of substituted benzamide observed at a lower acid concentration agrees with a similar observation of Edward and Meacock¹. Amides are strong bases appreciably protonated in 3*M* to 6*M* acid concentration. Below the concentration of the optimum rate, the effect of increasing acid concentration is primarily to increase the concentration of the protonated intermediate; above the concentration of optimum rate, the effect is mainly to decrease the concentration or activity of water⁷.

where seat of proton may be on oxygen or nitrogen.

The rate constants were determined at different acidities by keeping ionic strength constant. The results are shown in Table 2. From the values of

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH ON REACTION RATE AT 95°

	HClO ₄ <i>M</i>	NaClO ₄ <i>M</i>	Ionic strength μ	$K \times 10^3$ sec ⁻¹	$K_{H^+} \times 10^3$ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Benzamide	1.0	0.0	1.0	3.418	
	0.8	0.2	1.0	2.914	3.419
	0.6	0.4	1.0	2.104	
	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.554	
	2.0	0.0	2.0	5.362	
	1.5	0.5	2.0	3.967	2.740
	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.996	
	0.5	1.5	2.0	1.370	
	3.0	0.0	3.0	5.821	
	2.5	0.5	3.0	4.860	1.926
2.0	1.0	3.0	3.632		
1.5	1.5	3.0	3.025		
<i>m</i> -nitrobenzamide	0.5	0.0	0.5	3.760	
	0.4	0.1	0.5	3.015	7.522
	0.2	0.3	0.5	1.501	
	1.0	0.0	1.0	6.128	
	0.8	0.2	1.0	4.848	6.100
	0.5	0.5	1.0	3.057	
	2.0	0.0	2.0	7.515	
	1.5	0.5	2.0	5.420	3.656
1.0	1.0	2.0	3.600		
<i>p</i> -methylbenzamide	0.5	0.0	0.5	2.890	
	0.4	0.1	0.5	2.249	5.668
	0.3	0.2	0.5	1.681	
	1.0	0.0	1.0	4.946	
	0.8	0.2	1.0	3.643	3.637
	0.4	0.6	1.0	1.747	

rate coefficient at different acidities at a particular ionic strength, the reaction can be represented by the equation :

$$K = K_{H^+} C_{H^+} \quad \dots (1)$$

where K and K_{H^+} are the observed and specific rate constants.

Effect of ionic strength :

It is found that the values of specific rate K_{H^+} decreased with the increase in ionic strength. This leads to the conclusion that the reaction exhibits a negative ionic strength effect. In Fig. 1 it is observed that the plots representing rate coefficient at different acidities pass through the origin leading to the inference that the reaction due to neutral species is absent.

Further, these results indicate that the reaction proceeds via only protonated species which is subjected to negative salt effect. The rate data may be represented by a modified form of the Bionsted-Bjerrum equation⁹.

$$K = K_{H^+} C_{H^+} e^{-b\mu} (a_{H_2O})^n \quad \dots (2)$$

where a_{H_2O} is activity of water⁸, n is the number of water molecules and μ is ionic strength.

The values of $\log K_{H^+}$ are plotted against ionic strength (Fig. 2). From the plot, values of $K_{H_0^+}$ and b are calculated. $K_{H_0^+}$ is the intercept at zero-ionic

Fig. 2. Plots of rate coefficients vs ionic strengths.

- Benzamide
- *m*-nitrobenzamide
- △ *p*-methylbenzamide.

strength, and b is the slope of the line. The values of $K_{H_0^+}$ for benzamide, *m*-nitrobenzamide and *p*-methylbenzamide are 4.704×10^{-3} , 7.104×10^{-3} and 9.452×10^{-3} mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ respectively and the corresponding values of slopes b are 0.1, 0.15 and 0.18. The theoretical values of rate constants at different acidities were calculated using $n = 1$ in equation 2. These values are in close agreement with the experimental values as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF THE OBSERVED AND CALCULATED RATES FOR THE PERCHLORIC ACID CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF AMIDES AT 95°

HClO ₄	Benzamide			<i>m</i> -nitrobenzamide			<i>p</i> -methylbenzamide			^a H ₂ O
	Expt. K × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	Calc. K × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	K _{H₀} ⁺ × 10 ³ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Expt. K × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	Calc. K × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	K _{H₀} ⁺ × 10 ³ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Expt. K × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	Calc. K × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	K _{H₀} ⁺ × 10 ³ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	
0.5	2.06	2.05	4.71	3.76	3.76	9.41	2.89	2.92	6.81	0.98
1.0	3.42	3.58	4.67	6.12	6.00	9.46	4.95	4.82	7.20	0.96
2.0	5.36	5.39	4.70	7.51	7.50	9.45	6.50	6.47	7.10	0.91
3.0	5.82	5.86	4.70	6.70	6.78	9.46	6.28	6.27	6.91	0.83
4.0	5.52	5.46	4.75	5.22	5.25	9.38	5.12	5.20	7.12	0.73
5.0	4.61	4.53	4.76	3.68	3.63	9.58	—	—	—	0.61

Arrhenius parameters :

The values of Arrhenius parameters were calculated and are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4

	E Kcals/mole	A litre-mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	ΔS e.u.
Benzamide	19.21	12.38 × 10 ⁸	-41.82
<i>m</i> -nitrobenzamide	21.27	26.57 × 10 ⁹	-47.92
<i>p</i> -methylbenzamide	14.39	17.10 × 10 ⁵	-39.38

These values are in favour of bimolecular mechanism. It is found that an electron withdrawing group in amide increases the activation energy while an electron donating group decreases it. This is in agreement with the observation of Molechoe and Laidler¹⁰.

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References

1. J. T. EDWARD and S. C. MEACOCK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2000.
2. M. M. MAHALA and M. H. JAGDALE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **3**, 147.
3. D. ROSENTHAL and T. I. TAYLOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 2684.
4. C. K. INGOLD, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 1963, p. 784.
5. S. P. L. SORENSON in *Practical Organic Chemistry*, (Ed) F. C. Mann and B. C. Sunders, Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1953, p. 367.
6. N. F. HALL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 5115 and references cited there.
7. V. K. KRIEBLE and K. A. HOLST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2976.
8. J. E. LEFFLER and E. GRUNWALD, "Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York and London, 1963, p. 286.
9. F. A. LONG and W. F. McDEVOT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, **51**, 119.
10. I. MALOCHE and K. J. LAIDLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1712.